

Microstructure, microhardness and corrosion resistance of remelted TiG2 and Ti6Al4V by a high power diode laser

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ABSTRACT

The high strength, low density and superior corrosion resistance allow titanium alloys to be widely employed in different industrial applications. The properties of these alloys can be modulated by different heat treatments, including laser processing. In the present paper, laser remelting treatments, performed with a high power diode laser, were applied to samples of two titanium alloys (TiG2 and Ti6Al4V). The influence of the applied laser fluence on microstructure, microhardness and corrosion resistance is investigated. Results show that laser remelting treatments with appropriate fluences provoke microstructural changes leading to microhardness increase and corrosion resistance improvement.

Keywords:

- A. Titanium
- B. EIS
- B. Polarisation
- B. XRD
- C. Hardening

1. Introduction

Titanium and titanium alloys are widely employed in different fields (medical, aerospace, automotive, petrochemical, nuclear, power generation, etc.) due to their high strength, low density and good corrosion resistance as a consequence of the formation of very stable, continuous, highly adherent and protective oxide films on metal surfaces [1,2]. Nonetheless, some applications require improvements of these properties. Heat and thermomechanical treatments are known to modify the properties of these alloys. Among them, laser treatments, such as laser metal deposition (LMD), selective laser melting (SLM) or laser remelting (LR) are being currently employed to achieve this aim. Taking into account the reactivity at high temperatures of titanium and titanium alloys, LR treatments are more attractive than traditional heat treatments [2], because the processing time significantly decreases. Therefore, at the relatively high processing rates of laser treatments, the melting zone is kept at high temperatures for less time, limiting the risk of oxidation [2]. Moreover, the microstructure of rapidly solidified materials show clear advantages, such as refinement, reduced microsegregation, extended solid solubility and formation of metastable phases [3,4].

Although LR treatments have been widely reported to improve the mechanical and corrosion behaviour of different steels and aluminium alloys, relatively few studies have investigated the properties of LR titanium and titanium alloy samples [1,5-7]. LR treatments have been performed with different types of laser sources such as CO₂ laser, Nd:YAG laser, laser excimer and high power diode laser, the latter presenting lower maintenance costs and higher efficiency than the others, representing a clear economical advantage [8,9]. Thus, Sun et al. performed LR treatments on titanium (Grade 2) samples with a Nd:YAG laser [1]. A microstructure change from α phase to acicular martensite is reported, leading to microhardness increase in the remelted zone with respect to the base metal. Linear polarisation (LP) tests and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) showed that these treatments improve the corrosion behaviour in 3.5 wt.% NaCl solutions [1]. In

another study [5], surface treatments with excimer laser were applied to Ti6Al4V samples with the aim of improving the pitting corrosion resistance of the alloy. The influence of two different shielding gases, argon and nitrogen, was analysed. Excimer laser surface treatments were seen to increase the pitting potential of this alloy significantly, especially when the material was shielded with argon [5]. More recently, Zaveri et al. [6] have studied Ti6Al4V samples treated with a pulsed-wave Nd:YAG laser in which pure argon was employed as shielding gas. Different processing conditions were used to obtain surface oxide layers with high corrosion resistance. The laser-treated Ti6Al4V specimens were seen to have better corrosion resistance than the base metal in NaCl, Hank's and Cigada solutions. In [7], commercially pure (CP) titanium has been treated with a CO₂ laser, employing pure argon as shielding gas. LR treatments lead to the formation of martensite, microstructure reported to have a much higher microhardness (425 HV) than the CP Ti substrate (209 HV) [7].

As commented above, different laser sources have been used in the literature to perform remelting treatments on titanium alloys, in order to modify their properties. However, neither of these studies report the employment of high power diode lasers (HPDL) using pure argon as shielding gas. HPDL has only been employed with nitrogen as a shielding gas so far; aforementioned treatments leading to the formation of nitride layers on titanium alloys [10,11]. The influence of the laser fluence on the properties of Ti alloys remelted with HPDL is not reported in the literature either. The objective of the present work is to study the effect of laser remelting treatments, performed with a HPDL shielded with pure argon, on the properties of TiG2 and Ti6Al4V samples. The effect of the laser fluence on the microstructure, microhardness and corrosion resistance in NaCl solutions is analysed.

2. Materials and methods

TiG2 and Ti6Al4V samples of 32 x 32 x 3 mm, whose chemical compositions are given in Table 1, were employed as base material in this study. Before the laser treatments, the samples were cleaned with acetone and later sandblasted using white corindon particles to increase the radiation

absorption [12–14]. A high power diode laser (ROFIN-SINAR DL028S) has been employed to perform the different laser treatments, working at the focal distance (69.3 mm from the focusing lens). LR treatments were performed under conduction regime, the spot size on surface being $2.2 \times 1.7 \text{ mm}^2$ [12]. Fig. 1 includes a scheme of the set-up used to perform the LR treatments. Eleven linear parallel laser scans of 15 mm long were exerted on the samples. Each scan was separated 1.5 mm from the previous one, 16 s being the waiting time between scans to avoid overheating. These treatments allow a minimum remelted area of $15 \times 15 \text{ mm}^2$. The shielding gas was argon with a flow rate of 15 L/min, applied with a coaxial nozzle. Two parameters were modified, the power (P), the laser processing rates (v). Table 2 includes the parameter values employed in each laser remelting treatment. The fluence of the treatments was estimated with Eq. (1):

$$F = \frac{P}{v \cdot S_x} \quad (1)$$

where F is the fluence (kJ/cm^2), P is the laser power (kW), S_x is the width of the spot at the scan direction (x -axis, $S_x = 0.17 \text{ cm}$) and v is the laser processing rates (cm/s).

The microstructure and microhardness were evaluated with mounted cross-sections of the samples, after polishing and etching with Kroll's reagent. Microhardness measurements were measured with a Duramin microhardness tester of Struers. The charge employed was 2.945 N, during 19 s. These measurements were performed following the standard UNE-EN-ISO 6507:2006.

The crystalline phases generated with the LR treatments have been identified by X-ray diffraction (XRD), performed by a Bruker instrument, model D8 Advance (radius 250 mm). The diffractograms were recorded under the following conditions: Cu $K\alpha$ radiation, with graphite monochromator, scan range from 3° up to 75° , with a step size of 0.07° and a time per step of 40 s. From the XRD spectra, the crystal size and lattice strain of the BM and LR samples have been estimated by means of both Scherrer and Williamson–Hall Methods. It has to be taken into account that the crystal size is a measure of the coherently diffracting domains size, not being generally the

same as the grain size due to the formation of polycrystalline aggregates [15,16]. Lattice strain is a measure of the distribution of lattice constants arising from crystal imperfections, such as lattice dislocations [16]. The estimation of the crystal size by means of the Scherrer method is shown in Eq. (2):

$$D = \frac{k \cdot \lambda}{\beta_D \cdot \cos\theta'} \quad (2)$$

where D is the crystal size (in Å), k is the wavelength of the radiation (1.54056 Å for Cu K α radiation), k is a constant equal to 0.9, β_D is the main peak width at half maximum intensity and θ is the peak position [16]. The breadth of the Bragg peak depends on both instrumental and sample effects. To decouple these contributions, it is necessary to collect a diffraction pattern from the line broadening of a standard material to determine the instrumental broadening (in our case, the standard was lanthanum hexaboride, reference NIST: SRM660A).

The instrument-corrected broadening b_D was then calculated from Eq. (3) [15,16]:

$$\beta_D^2 = [(\beta^2)_{\text{measured}} - (\beta^2)_{\text{instrument}}]. \quad (3)$$

The Williamson–Hall Method was also employed to estimate both the crystal size (D) and the lattice strain (ε). By means of Eq. (4), a linear relationship between the width at half-maximum intensity of the different peaks of the spectra (β_{hkl}) and their corresponding θ can be established, in which the slope of the equation allows the estimation of ε , and the y-intercept is related to D :

$$\beta_{hkl} \cdot \cos\theta = \left(\frac{k\lambda}{D}\right) + (4 \cdot \varepsilon \cdot \sin\theta) \quad (4)$$

Electrochemical corrosion tests were performed on the treated samples. In order to obtain smooth

and homogeneous surface, remelted samples were ground up to 1200 grit with SiC paper before the corrosion tests. In each test, 3 h of open circuit potential (E_{oc}) was measured with the objective of letting the corrosion potential stabilise. Subsequently, EIS measurements were performed under potentiodynamic mode with a voltage perturbation amplitude of 20 mV vs. corrosion potential, in the frequency range from 10^4 to 10^{-3} Hz. Similarly to EIS measurements, various LP curves were registered in different ranges (from -0.150 to $+2.000$ V vs. E_{oc}) after 5 h of E_{oc} , at a polarisation rate of 0.1667 mV/s. From LP curves, some parameters could be obtained, such as the polarisation resistance, R_p , (estimated in the range between ± 20 mV vs. E_{oc}) and the corrosion current density, i_{corr} , (determined by Tafel's slopes in the range between ± 150 mV vs. E_{oc}) [17,18]. In the LP curves registered up to $+2.000$ V vs. E_{oc} , evidence of breakdown potentials was not observed in any sample. Additional electrochemical parameters (the protective efficiency, P_e , and total porosity, P) have been estimated from the LP curves, with the objective of exploring their applicability to perform a deeper investigation of the corrosion behaviour of the samples. As far as the authors are concerned, these two parameters have only been applied to the study of coating so far [19–26]. P_e has been estimated by Eq. (5), following the method given in Ref. [19].

$$P_e = 100 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{i_{corr}}{i_{corr}^0} \right) \quad (5)$$

where i_{corr} is the corrosion current density of the LR samples and i_{corr}^0 the corrosion current density of the base metal. P has been calculated using Elsener's empirical Eq. (6) [27]:

$$P = \frac{R_p^0}{R_p} \cdot 10^{-|\Delta E_{corr}/\beta_a|} \quad (6)$$

where R_p^0 is the polarisation resistance of base metal; R_p , the polarisation resistance of the LR

samples; ΔE_{corr} , the difference between the E_{oc} of the LR samples and that of the base metal; and b_a , the anodic Tafel slope of the base metal.

A conventional three-electrode cell arrangement was employed, using a reference electrode of Ag/AgCl with 3 M KCl (+0.207 V vs. SHE) and a graphite bar as counter electrode. The electrolyte was 3.5 wt.% NaCl aerated solution at room temperature. The area exposed to the electrolyte was 1 cm². The electrochemical measurements were performed with a 1287 potentiostat connected to a 1255 frequency response analyser (FRA), both of Solartron. The data analyses were performed with Scribner softwares: CorrView was employed to study LP curves and ZView was used to fit the EIS spectra to the appropriated equivalent circuit. From both techniques, R_p could be estimated.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Microstructure, microhardness and corrosion resistance of LR TiG2 samples

Metallographic images of TiG2 base metal (TiG2-BM) and some laser remelted (LR) TiG2 samples (TiG2-T1, TiG2-T5 and TiG2-T8; with T1, T5 and T8 laser treatments, respectively) are shown in Fig. 2. The microstructure of TiG2-BM (Fig. 2(a)) consists of Ti- α type equiaxial grains with a relatively uniform grain size (average around 80-100 μ m). This microstructure is similar to the one previously reported for this alloy [28–31]. According to Fig. 2(b), (c) and (d), LR treatments are seen to modify the shape and size of the grains. In order to better characterise the microstructure after the LR treatments, cross-sections of samples could be divided into three zones, each 1 mm thick, identified as A, B and C zones (the upper surface of A zone being the interface irradiated with laser). The average grain size (G_R) in each zone has been measured and plotted in Fig. 3. Data of Fig. 3 show that, in all LR conditions, the A zone presents higher grains than B and C zones (higher GR). In the A zone, the grain size is more irregular and the grain shape becomes more elongated than in B and C zones. In this A zone of LR samples, the developed

microstructure consists of serrated Ti- α grains with greater size than the base metal, together with some fine acicular α grains, as shown in Fig. 4. This microstructure has already been observed in a previous work [32], in which CP Titanium samples were welded with a pulse Nd:YAG laser. Clear evidences of martensite could not be observed either in Ref. [19] or in our samples. These results contrast with those previously published in Refs. [1,7], in which martensite formation had been reported for CP Titanium remelted with a Nd:YAG pulsed laser [1] and with a continuous wave CO₂ laser [7], probably due to the relatively higher cooling rates of these latter LR treatments.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements have been performed on TiG2-BM and LR TiG2 samples. Fig. 5 shows the XRD spectra of TiG2-BM and TiG2-T2 samples. The obtained results allowed us to confirm that only a phase (hcp) is present in TiG2-BM and in all LR samples. Therefore, LR treatments do not provoke phase transformation in CP Titanium samples. Table 3 reports the values of the crystal size, D (by both Scherrer and Williamson–Hall methods) and lattice strain, ϵ (by Williamson–Hall method) of BM and LR TiG2 samples. Here, only the results of one LR sample (TiG2-T2) has been considered, as all LR TiG2 samples provided the same microstructure. The Scherrer method provides a better approach for the estimation of D than the Williamson–Hall method, because the former only takes into account the main peak of the α phase, while the latter performs the calculation with all XRD peaks, some of them being relatively weak (leading consequently to more noticeable errors in the estimation of β_{hkl}). Thus, the Scherrer method has been taken into account to discuss the D values. As shown in Table 3, both BM and LR TiG2 samples have shown similar Scherrer results ($D = 36\text{--}37$ nm). These values are observed to be more than three orders of magnitude lower than the grain size measured from metallographic observations (around 100 μm). As explained before, these results are reasonable, as D is strictly related to the crystal size, the grains are formed by numerous nanocrystals with different orientations. Therefore, LR treatments seem to enlarge the grain size without modifying the size of their nanocrystals. Regarding the lattice strain, LR TiG2 samples

are observed to have higher ϵ values than TiG2-BM samples (Table 3). These results were expected, considering that LR treatments induced certain strain in the TiG2 grains. TiG2-BM samples present a small negative $\beta_{hkl} - \theta$ slope, surely because the real value of ϵ is close to zero (lattice strain negligible).

In LR TiG2 samples, the microhardness varies along the depth of the samples as shown in Fig. 6. In all treatments, the microhardness values of A zone (zone directly irradiated by laser) are significantly higher than the values of zone B and C. Thus, the microhardness values of A zone range between 140 and 200 HV. Little differences are found between the B and C zones, both having microhardness values close to the untreated TiG2-BM samples (114 HV). The microhardness values of these zones are related to their microstructures: while the A zone presents elongated serrated Ti- α grains and acicular α -grains microstructure, B and C zones show equiaxial grains with a similar size. Therefore, the microstructure of A zone presents more grain boundaries than B and C zones, leading to higher microhardness values.

Some representative polarisation curves of TiG2 samples (always performed in zone A) are included in Fig. 7. The anodic branches of the curves show a clear passivity zone, reflecting low corrosion activity of all systems. Table 4 reports the obtained values of E_{oc} , i_{corr} , P and P_e for the LR and base metal samples. The values of E_{oc} and i_{corr} are observed to fall in the range between -0.200 and -0.450 V vs. Ag/AgCl 3 M KCl and between 5 and 35 nA/cm², a clear tendency allowing one to distinguish between different samples has not been observed. Concerning the protective efficiency parameter, P_e , both positive and negative values were obtained, always presenting a high standard deviation. These disperse values are thought to be a consequence of highly scattered values of i_{corr} obtained for each system, together with the fact that all systems presented similar i_{corr} values. The values of the total porosity, P , also showed high dispersion, surely due to the similar R_p values of the samples. The detailed microstructural observation did not detect the presence of microporous in the LR samples. It

is worth noting that these two latter parameters are mainly employed to characterise the corrosion properties of coatings, not having been applied yet to the study of laser remelting treatments. In fact, according to the obtained results, these parameters do not seem to provide detailed information regarding the corrosion protection and porosity of the remelted material.

Examples of Nyquist and bode EIS spectra of samples are also represented in Fig. 8. These EIS spectra were fitted to the Randles circuit, shown in Fig. 9. This equivalent circuit was seen to provide the best fitting to the EIS spectra of both TiG2 and Ti6Al4V treated and untreated samples, in which R_s is the solution resistance, CPE the constant phase element and R_p the polarisation resistance [6]. A good agreement between experimental and simulated spectra was found, as depicted in Fig. 10. Mean (\pm standard deviation) values of R_s , CPE and R_p of the simulated data of TiG2 samples are included in Table 5; n values always range between 0.8 and 0.9. From the LP curves and simulated EIS spectra, R_p values of TiG2 samples were estimated and jointly plotted in Fig. 11. A reasonable agreement is observed between R_p values estimated by both techniques. As can be seen in the figure, almost all values of BM and LR titanium samples range between 1 and 4 $M\Omega\text{ cm}^2$. Taking into account the relatively high dispersion between different replicates of TiG2 samples, it can be generally stated that R_p values are statistically similar for all treatments. These results were expected, considering the similar microstructure developed in all TiG2 samples. Therefore, both TiG2-BM and LR TiG2 samples have similar corrosion resistance in NaCl solutions.

From the results obtained in this section, it can be summarised that LR treatments performed with HPDL shielded with argon, allowed the TiG2 samples to change the shape and size of their grains without provoking phase transformations. Furthermore, LR increases the microhardness of TiG2 without affecting their corrosion behaviour in 3.5 wt.% NaCl solutions.

3.2. *Microstructure, microhardness and corrosion resistance of LR Ti6Al4V samples*

As can be observed in Fig. 12(a), the microstructure of Ti6Al4V base metal (Ti6Al4V-BM) comprises two phases: equiaxed α with intergranular β [31,33]. The microstructure of LR Ti6Al4V samples (Fig. 12(b)–(g)) is significantly different from that observed in Ti6Al4V-BM (Fig. 12(a)). Two different patterns have been identified in the LR Ti6Al4V samples, depending on the input laser fluence applied. Thus, as observed in Fig. 12(b)–(d), high fluences (LR treatments T1 to T3, with laser fluences between 10 and 30 kJ/cm²) generate two zones, melted zone (MZ) and heat affected zone (HAZ). Both zones are composed of clear defined grains with microlaminar β in α matrix microstructure. The grains of MZ are bigger and more elongated than those generated in HAZ. This laminar $\alpha + \beta$ microstructure are thought to be due to the relatively low cooling rate of these LR treatments. Meanwhile, at low and medium fluencies (T4 to T8, 0.8–10 kJ/cm²), three zones are generally identified, as shown in Fig. 12(e)–(g): melted zone (MZ), heat affected zone (HAZ) and base metal (BM). The microstructure of MZ is characterised by presenting martensite acicular α' ; HAZ consists of a mixture of $\alpha + \beta$; and BM is formed by equiaxed α with intergranular β , the same microstructure than that observed in Ti6Al4V-BM samples. In T4 to T8 LR treatments, martensitic micro-structure is generated in the MZ, as a consequence of the high heating and cooling rates [2,28,29]. A similar microstructure has been recently observed in selective laser melting (SLM) of Ti6Al4V performed with a Yb:YAG fibre laser [34] and a Nd:YAG laser [35].

The described microstructures of Ti6Al4V samples have been confirmed by XRD measurements. Fig. 13(a) shows diffractograms (in the range of 2θ between 30° and 75°) of different zones of samples: Ti6Al4V-BM ($\alpha + \beta$ microstructure), Ti6Al4V-T2 (MZ) (alternated $\alpha + \beta$ microstructure), Ti6Al4V-T5 (MZ) (α' martensite) and Ti6Al4V-T8 (HAZ) ($\alpha + \beta$ microstructure). The hcp pattern can be attributed to both α -phase and the α' martensite, as they have the same crystalline structure and very similar lattice parameters [35–38]. It is clearly observed in Fig. 13(a) that the main peaks of all spectra are assigned to α or α' phase (hcp), as

the β phase (bcc) is always minority or absent. The range of 2θ between 37° and 41° has been amplified in Fig. 13(b), as it contains the main peak attributed to β phase, at $2\theta = 39.5^\circ$ [35,38]. Indeed, a weak peak appears at this angle in Ti6Al4V (BM), its intensity decreasing in Ti6Al4V-T2 (MZ), surely due to the microlaminar microstructure generated, disappearing in samples Ti6Al4V-T5 (MZ) and Ti6Al4V-T8 (HAZ). In Fig. 13(b), it is also noticeable that the intensity of the peak appearing at 38.5° (associated to α phase) decreases from Ti6Al4V-BM to Ti6Al4V-T2 (MZ) and to Ti6Al4V-T8 (HAZ), completely vanishing in Ti6Al4V-T5 (MZ). This feature is associated to the α' martensitic phase, which seems to not give peaks at 39.5° (α phase) or at 38.5° (β phase). Table 6 includes D (by both the Scherrer and Williamson–Hall methods) and ε (by the Williamson–Hall method) values of the α phase of BM and LR Ti6Al4V samples. Again, only samples with representative microstructures have been analysed by these two methods. The β phase could not be analysed because it only provided a very weak peak in the XRD spectra (Fig. 13). As in TiG2 samples, only the Scherrer method was considered for the discussion of D . The crystal sizes of Ti6Al4V samples (Table 6) are observed to be significantly smaller than the values of TiG2 samples (Table 3).

According to Table 6, Ti6Al4V-BM (α phase) and Ti6Al4V-T5 (α' phase) samples have similar D values, the Ti6Al4V-T2 (α phase) sample presenting slightly smaller values and the Ti6Al4V-T8 (α phase of HAZ) showing marginally higher values. Concerning ε values, α' phase (martensite in Ti6Al4V-T5) is observed to have the highest lattice strain, followed by the α phase of the HAZ (of Ti6Al4V-T8). Both Ti6Al4V-BM and Ti6Al4V-T2 (α phase) are seen to have small negative values of ε , perhaps due to the negligible lattice strain. These ε results are reasonable, as the α' martensite is the phase providing highest lattice strain.

Concerning the microhardness measurements, the higher values are always measured in MZ of all LR Ti6Al4V samples, followed by HAZ, as shown in Fig. 14. However, a different microhardness pattern is observed in samples with high fluence treatments (T1 to T3) in

comparison with those with low and medium fluencies (T4 to T8). Thus, at low and medium fluencies (F lower than 10 kJ/cm^2), values around 426 HV are reached in MZ, decreasing to 400 HV in HAZ and to 330 HV in BM. Hence, differences around 100 HV between MZ and BM are observed. These disparities are associated to the formation of a martensite microstructure. On the other hand, the microhardness of the MZ in Ti6Al4V samples with T1 to T3 LR treatments (F higher than 10 kJ/cm^2) is significantly lower (around 390 HV) than the measured in samples with T4 to T8 treatments (around 426 HV), but higher than that measured in base metal (around 333 HV). These microhardness values (in Ti6Al4V-T1 to T3 samples) are attributed to the microstructure developed (microlaminar $\alpha + \beta$ phases inside grains). The formation of this microstructure may be a consequence of the relatively low cooling rates (in comparison with T4 to T8 treatments) of the melting pool during the LR treatments.

Fig. 15 shows some LP curves of Ti6Al4V samples. The values of E_{oc} , i_{corr} , P and P_e of BM and LR Ti6Al4V samples are included in Table 7. E_{oc} and i_{corr} values are seen to be similar to those measured in LR TiG2 samples, E_{oc} ranging between -0.200 and -0.400 V vs. Ag/AgCl 3 M KCl and i_{corr} between 5 and 20 nA/cm^2 . Similarly to LR TiG2 samples, in LR Ti6Al4V samples P_e and P parameters provide rather scattered values. It is difficult to find noticeable tendencies in these four parameters when comparing the values of different samples. As previously described, the microstructure of LR Ti6Al4V samples does not show any evidence of microporous formation. According to these results, P_e and P parameters do not seem to give relevant information about the corrosion properties of LR samples.

Fig. 16 depicts some representative EIS spectra of Ti6Al4V samples. Table 8 illustrates electrical parameters of the equivalent circuit obtained by fitting the EIS experimental results of Ti6Al4V samples. From the LP curves (Fig. 15) and EIS spectra (Fig. 16), R_p values could be estimated. Again, a meaningful correspondence between R_p values estimated by both techniques is observed, as shown in Fig. 17. Comparing these values with those reported in the previous section

for TiG2 samples (Fig. 11), it can easily be observed that both alloys lead to similar R_p values, ranging between 0.5 and 7 $M\Omega\text{ cm}^2$. Although the R_p values show high dispersion, some differences in corrosion behaviour can be found between the LR Ti6Al4V samples. Thus, R_p values of BM are observed to be similar to the ones obtained in samples with high fluences LR treatments (T1 to T3), ranging from 0.5 to 3.5 $M\Omega\text{ cm}^2$. Although these samples show clearly different microstructures, both consisting of α and β phases. This may be the reason for the similar corrosion behaviour. Ti6Al4V samples subjected to medium fluences LR treatments (T4 to T7) showed the best corrosion behaviour, giving R_p values between 0.5 and 7 $M\Omega\text{ cm}^2$. This corrosion resistance improvement is attributed to the developed of martensitic α' microstructure. Finally, the lowest R_p values were measured in the HAZ zone of samples with T8 treatment (values between 1 and 2 $M\Omega\text{ cm}^2$). The microstructure developed in the HAZ is seen to give the worst corrosion resistance in NaCl solutions.

In order to relate the energy applied in the LR treatments with the volume of melted material, the depth of the MZ of the different LR Ti6Al4V samples, defined here as M_D , has been measured from metallographic images. These values have been represented in function of the total input laser fluence (F), Fig. 18. A linear correlation between M_D and F is observed. Eq. (7) shows the line that best fits to the obtained experimental data:

$$M_D = a + bF \quad (7)$$

where a and b are constants (0.3995 mm and 0.0469 mm cm^2/kJ , respectively). M_D is expressed in mm and F in kJ/cm^2 . This figure clearly shows that the fusion zone volume of LR Ti6Al4V samples is directly proportional to the applied energy in the LR treatments. Therefore, keeping the experimental conditions invariable, it is possible to estimate the penetration of the MZ taking into account the applied laser fluence. In other words, the linear relationship between M_D and F permits a precise control of the martensite depth in LR Ti6Al4V samples.

To sum up, LR treatments are seen to provoke important effects on microstructure,

microhardness and corrosion behaviour of Ti6Al4V samples. Thus, LR treatments with fluences below 10 kJ/cm^2 allow the formation of α' martensite, microstructure leading to significant microhardness increase and corrosion improvement, in comparison with other phases. The depth of martensite zone is seen to be directly proportional to F , this relationship allowing the preparation of samples with the desired depth of martensitic phase.

4. Conclusions

In TiG2 samples, LR treatments lead to a grain size increase, the grains becoming elongated. The microstructure developed consisted of serrated Ti- α and fine acicular α grains. Microhardness is seen to increase with laser fluence, as a consequence of the microstructural changes. LR treatments do not seem to alter the corrosion resistance of TiG2 samples significantly, probably because they do not produce phase transformations. Therefore, LR treatments of TiG2 samples allow one to increase the microhardness without affecting the corrosion resistance.

In LR Ti6Al4V samples, two distinct patterns have been observed: at high fluences (F between 10 and 30 kJ/cm^2) only two zones are identified (MZ and HAZ) and at low and medium fluencies (F between 0.5 and 10 kJ/cm^2), three zones are identified (MZ, HAZ and BM). At high fluences, laminar $\alpha + \beta$ microstructure is generated in the MZ, while at low and medium fluencies the microstructure consists of α' martensite. Low fluences (F lower than 1 kJ/cm^2) lead to very thin martensitic layers. The martensitic microstructure showed a significant microhardness increase and corrosion resistance improvement in comparison with the other microstructures.

A linear relationship between the depth of the melted zone (MD) and F is observed in LR Ti6Al4V samples. This relationship allows the design of experimental procedures able to control the depth of martensitic phase in these samples precisely.

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Element	Al	V	Fe	C	Element remains (maximum %)	Element remains (total %)	Ti
Ti6Al4V	5.67	4.50	0.18	0.010	60.10	60.40	Balance
TiG2	–	–	0.039	0.012	60.10	60.40	Balance

Table 1. Chemical composition of titanium alloys (wt.%).

Laser treatments	P (kW)	v (m/min)	F (kJ/cm ²)	Classification of F
T1	2.0	0.25	28.24	High
T2	2.0	0.30	23.53	
T3	2.0	0.45	15.69	
T4	2.5	1.00	8.82	Medium
T5	2.0	1.00	7.06	
T6	2.5	2.00	4.41	
T7	2.0	2.00	3.53	
T8	2.0	8.00	0.88	Low

Table 2. Experimental conditions of laser remelting treatments.

Sample	Scherrer method	Williamson–Hall method	
	D (Å)	D (Å)	ε ($\times 10^{-3}$, no units)
α (TiG2-BM)	370.85	284.57	-0.6756
α (TiG2-T2)	363.36	1187.35	1.1662

Table 3. Crystal size and lattice strain of BM and LR TiG2 samples.

Laser treatments TiG2	E_{corr} (V vs. Ag/AgCl 3 M KCl)	i_{corr} (nA/cm ²)	P_e (%)	P
Base metal	-0.376 ± 0.024	17.03 ± 8.12	—	—
T1	-0.240 ± 0.137	24.10 ± 10.46	41.46 ± 61.43	0.420 ± 0.412
T2	-0.309 ± 0.05	31.86 ± 39.18	-87.05 ± 230.47	0.962 ± 1.156
T3	-0.324 ± 0.021	15.33 ± 3.16	9.99 ± 18.58	0.570 ± 0.136
T4	-0.365 ± 0.123	12.95 ± 5.13	23.97 ± 30.14	0.224 ± 0.082
T5	-0.358 ± 0.045	8.760 ± 3.14	48.58 ± 18.46	0.391 ± 0.167
T6	-0.422 ± 0.118	15.95 ± 11.54	6.38 ± 67.74	0.505 ± 0.520
T7	-0.316 ± 0.016	14.44 ± 6.05	2.62 ± 35.53	0.557 ± 0.130
T8	-0.336 ± 0.054	20.05 ± 20.27	-17.69 ± 119.02	0.798 ± 0.176

Table 4. Electrochemical parameters of BM and LR TiG2 samples: corrosion potential (E_{corr}), current density (i_{corr}), protective efficiency (P_e) and total porosity (P).

Laser treatments TiG2	R_s (Ω cm ²)	R_p (M Ω cm ²)	CPE ($\times 10^{-5}$, $\Omega^{-1} S^n$ cm ²)	n
Base metal	21.58 \pm 6.59	2.02 \pm 1.53	1.00 \pm 0.36	0.89 \pm 0.02
T1	16.57 \pm 3.81	1.11 \pm 0.59	1.77 \pm 2.36	0.83 \pm 0.13
T2	22.40 \pm 6.88	1.89 \pm 1.50	3.78 \pm 1.38	0.90 \pm 0.06
T3	19.92 \pm 2.89	1.84 \pm 0.93	3.13 \pm 0.31	0.91 \pm 0.03
T4	21.89 \pm 2.04	3.06 \pm 0.58	2.65 \pm 0.64	0.92 \pm 0.01
T5	21.16 \pm 4.51	3.21 \pm 3.62	2.72 \pm 0.35	0.92 \pm 0.02
T6	18.68 \pm 5.51	2.39 \pm 1.66	2.66 \pm 0.25	0.90 \pm 0.01
T7	19.01 \pm 3.23	2.02 \pm 1.49	3.18 \pm 0.60	0.92 \pm 0.01
T8	22.43 \pm 4.44	1.72 \pm 1.52	2.70 \pm 1.48	0.91 \pm 0.01

Table 5. Electrical parameters of the equivalent circuit obtained by fitting the EIS spectra of TiG2 samples.

Sample	Scherrer method	Williamson–Hall method	
	D (Å)	D (Å)	ε ($\times 10^{-3}$, no units)
α (Ti6Al4V-BM)	239.00	345.26	-0.4905
α (Ti6Al4V-T2) (MZ)	250.40	322.87	-0.124
α' (Ti6Al4V-T5) (MZ)	240.57	3212.91	2.6592
α (Ti6Al4V-T8) (HAZ)	185.67	449.91	1.8812

Table 6. Crystal size and lattice strain of BM and LR Ti6Al4V samples.

Laser treatments	E_{corr} (V vs. Ag/AgCl 3 M KCl)	i_{corr} (nA/cm ²)	P_e (%)	P
Ti6Al4V				
Base metal	-0.383 ± 0.059	16.60 ± 6.20	–	–
T1	-0.335 ± 0.045	16.23 ± 1.07	2.21 ± 6.44	0.313 ± 0.174
T2	-0.230 ± 0.089	16.53 ± 7.99	0.40 ± 48.13	0.080 ± 0.05
T3	-0.235 ± 0.061	11.86 ± 3.78	28.51 ± 22.83	0.079 ± 0.05
T4	-0.250 ± 0.117	9.63 ± 6.09	42.07 ± 36.95	0.120 ± 0.117
T5	-0.288 ± 0.063	10.68 ± 1.07	-3.61 ± 64.28	0.209 ± 0.152
T6	-0.390 ± 0.034	12.33 ± 5.40	-1.00 ± 1.28	0.544 ± 0.156
T7	-0.353 ± 0.040	8.650 ± 3.60	47.89 ± 21.77	0.200 ± 0.019
T8	-0.342 ± 0.036	16.80 ± 2.12	-1.20 ± 12.75	0.333 ± 0.098

Table 7. Electrochemical parameters of BM and LR Ti6Al4V samples: corrosion potential (E_{corr}), current density (i_{corr}), protective efficiency (P_e) and total porosity (P).

Laser treatments Ti6Al4V	R_s ($\Omega \text{ cm}^2$)	R_p ($M \Omega \text{ cm}^2$)	CPE ($\times 10^{-5}, \Omega^{-1} \text{ S}^n \text{ cm}^2$)	n
Base metal	22.17 ± 7.08	1.76 ± 1.02	1.04 ± 16.60	0.93 ± 0.02
T1	21.08 ± 2.91	1.26 ± 1.70	2.37 ± 0.17	0.91 ± 0.01
T2	25.86 ± 7.00	1.56 ± 1.35	1.37 ± 1.06	0.89 ± 0.04
T3	28.50 ± 7.02	5.14 ± 3.82	1.54 ± 0.54	0.90 ± 0.04
T4	21.25 ± 3.89	3.85 ± 1.44	1.86 ± 39.6	0.93 ± 0.01
T5	18.79 ± 1.33	3.16 ± 3.46	1.85 ± 1.15	0.88 ± 0.03
T6	19.87 ± 2.15	1.40 ± 0.11	3.10 ± 0.15	0.90 ± 0.02
T7	19.78 ± 2.79	4.62 ± 3.46	2.29 ± 4.95	0.93 ± 0.00
T8	20.64 ± 2.03	1.30 ± 0.19	1.81 ± 1.57	0.92 ± 0.01

Table 8. Electrical parameters of the equivalent circuit obtained by fitting the EIS spectra of Ti6Al4V samples.

Fig. 1. Scheme of the set-up used to perform the LR treatments.

Fig. 2. Microstructure of BM and LR TiG2 samples: (a) TiG2-BM, (b) TiG2-T1, (c) TiG2-T5 and (d) TiG2-T8.

Fig. 3. Representative grain size (G_R) of the three different zones of LR TiG2 samples.

Fig. 4. Microstructure of zone A of TiG2-T1. Serrated α grains (S) and fine acicular α grains (A).

Fig. 5. XRD patterns of TiG2-BM and TiG2-T2 samples.

Fig. 6. Microhardness of the three different zones of remelted TiG2 samples.

Fig. 7. Potentiodynamic polarisation curves of TiG2 samples.

Fig. 8. Nyquist and bode diagrams of TiG2 samples.

Fig. 9. Equivalent circuit used to fit EIS spectra.

Fig. 10. Experimental and simulated EIS spectra of TiG2-T2.

Fig. 11. R_p values of TiG2 from the LP curves and simulated EIS spectra.

Fig. 12. Microstructure of Ti6Al4V samples: (a) Ti6Al4V-BM, (b–d) Ti6Al4V-T3 and (e–g)

Ti6Al4V-T5.

Fig. 13. XRD spectra of Ti6Al4V-BM, Ti6Al4V-T2 (MZ), Ti6Al4V-T5 (MZ) and Ti6Al4V-T8 (HAZ) in the range of 2θ between (a) 30–75° and (b) 37–41°.

Fig. 14. Microhardness of LR Ti6Al4V samples.

Fig. 15. Potentiodynamic polarisation curves of Ti6Al4V samples.

Fig. 16. Nyquist and bode plots of Ti6Al4V samples

Fig. 17. R_p values of Ti6Al4V from the LP curves and simulated EIS spectra.

Fig. 18. Correlation between M_D and F in LR Ti6Al4V samples.

